

COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT OF STITCHED FRP LAMINATES WITH MACHINED HOLES VERSUS BALLISTIC IMPACT PENETRATION APERTURES

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SUMMARY

Thin stitched carbon fiber reinforced composite (CFRP) panels were subjected to ballistic impacts from 30 caliber spherical steel projectiles at velocities ranging from 60 to 380 ms^{-1} . Compression after impact (CAI) testing was conducted to determine the residual strength after impact damage. Ballistic samples were also compared with machined clean-hole samples. A relationship was found between the minimum residual ballistic strength and the residual open-hole strength. Residual ballistic strength could be interpreted from less expensive clean-hole tests. It was determined that the minimum residual ballistic strength was 45% of the residual open-hole strength. This resulted in a simplified method for testing residual ballistic strength for a single projectile threat to this material. These results were also compared with previously tested E-glass/vinyl ester (EG/VE) composites.

INTRODUCTION

The weight reduction capabilities of incorporating composite materials into structures have been well documented [1-12]. The high specific strengths of composites have made laminate materials especially attractive in the aerospace, automotive, and marine environments where weight is directly related to performance and fuel consumption. Unfortunately, the cost of a composite's high strength and stiffness is poor toughness and impact properties [6,8]. This is mainly due to the inability for the laminate to plastically deform and absorb impact energy as observed in metals [1,10,12]. Composites instead dissipate impact energy via delamination, matrix cracking, fiber tension, shear plugging, and to a lesser extent friction during penetration [4,10]. The matrix cracking and interface delamination propagate toward the distal side in a conical shape from the point of impact [1,10]. Both matrix and fiber are shear rate dependent. Lower shear rate impacts would be dominated by fiber tension and delamination, whereas, very high shear rates would witness more shear plugging. As strain rates increase, delamination damage should theoretically be reduced to a point comparable to that of a clean drilled hole.

E-glass/vinyl ester (EG/VE) composite laminates are routinely featured in marine applications such as a ship structure deck, hull, and radar mast. Carbon fiber/vinyl ester (CF/VE) composites have recently attributed interest in replacing structural components in marine applications due to the higher specific strength. CFRP materials are not commonly used in marine applications; however, studies by Y. Aoki et al exhibited that CFRP materials are well suited for use in a marine environment. In fact, they appeared to

perform slightly better ballistically in the marine environment due to the small amount of absorbed water [2].

Military applications require additional precautions due to hazards such as ballistic, fragmentation, and blast events; leading to significant reduction in residual mechanical properties. A ballistic attack (which is the focus of this study) may lead to large scale localized damage to composite structures, and significantly reduce the load carrying capacity. This could potentially lead to catastrophic failure and collapse of the supported structure. Characterization of these residual mechanical properties is critical for military design purposes. To maximize the ballistic performance of composite structures, recent studies have shown that the volume content of the resin should be minimized to approximately 20% [9].

CRFPs are commonly drilled and held in place with bolted fixtures. S. Bartus and co-workers, was able to experimentally show that the ballistic limit was increased near previous ballistic holes, however, there has been little research done in characterizing the effect of a clean drilled hole in the damaged region associated with a ballistic event [10]. Bartus's work demonstrated how a more flexible structure has the ability to absorb more ballistic energy. In his study, the increased flexibility was due to the ballistic damage from a previous event. Flexibility can also be attained by creating a weakened fiber/matrix interface or utilizing more flexible fiber architectures.

Pegoretti et al. [13] determined that the flexibility of a composite is directly related to the interfacial contact area. They went further and identified that the absorbed impact energy was inversely proportional to the interface contact area. This was controlled via a film laid between laminates. The PET film was selectively partitioned to physically control the contact area where resin could create a bridge between fibers. Although this study was conducted on LVI, these results would intuitively hold true for HVI events as well.

The structural applications would not necessarily need to be ballistic grade. At extremely low impact velocities, minimal damage is expected; increasing to the maximum damage caused at the ballistic limit velocity [3]. At very high velocities, the shear rate should increase to a point of total shear plugging causing no energy dissipation through delamination [7]. This scenario would resemble a clean hole. Therefore, the residual strength as a function of impact velocity should start high, drop significantly, and then increase after ballistic penetration. This increase should plateau according to the residual strength associated with the clean-hole.

This study is an attempt to characterize the relationship between ballistically damaged and clean-hole specimens. Impact velocities encapsulate the pre- and post- perforation ranges with a hope to capture the shift to shear plugging failure. Establishing the damage-residual property relationship between clean-hole damage to ballistic damage would lead to a simple evaluation method for multipoint impact conditions. The CAI test is the standard method used to determine residual compressive strength in a thin laminate after impact.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A large panel of CF/VE was fabricated using a Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) process. Eight layers of SAERTEX 0/90 HTA 12k/6k CF were infused with Derakane 510A-40 VE resin. This resulted in thirty four 4"x 6"x 4.5mm machined panels with a fiber volume fraction of 45%. Ballistic testing utilized a single stage gas gun and photoelectric chronographs to detect projectile velocity. Stainless steel 0.3 inch diameter ball bearings were used as projectiles propelled by a foam sabot. The CAI testing was conducted on a SAETEC load frame using a CAI test fixture and Omega strain gages to ensure the compressive failure.

The EG/VE panels were also made using the VARTM method. Two separate plates were created with a large-tow plain woven E-glass; one for ballistic and the other for clean (drilled) holes. Comprehensive testing was conducted, but only the results from CAI testing will be reported in this paper. The clean-hole samples have a 30% resin volume fraction, and the ballistic samples 34% resin volume fraction. The samples were 4"x 6"x 5.3mm machined laminates.

Impact and CAI Tests

Samples were subjected to ballistic impact from a spherical round via nitrogen fed gas gun. Impact velocities ranged from 60 to 380 ms^{-1} with a ballistic limit determined to be close to 225 ms^{-1} . Two sets of photoelectric chronographs recorded both the incident and exit velocities of the projectile.

CAI testing was conducted in accordance with ASTM D 7137 standard. Figure 1(a) shows the residual compressive strength of the impacted composites at their respective impact velocities. Figure 1(b) indicates the relation of clean-hole specimens in comparison to the ballistically impacted specimens.

Figures 1: (a) (Left) displays the residual strength after impact at various velocities. (b) (Right) represents the residual strength of clean-hole samples.

As anticipated, the residual strength decreased as the impact velocity increased and caused more damage. The maximum damage was observed at the ballistic limit. Residual strength dropped from approximately 160 MPa to 55 MPa (34%). This was a drastic difference when compared to the drilled clean-hole specimens at 132 MPa (83%). An unexpected result was that the penetrated specimens did not appear to witness any decrease in damage due to increased strain rates. For this particular material configuration the residual strength comparison between the machined hole samples and the ballistic samples (at maximum damage) are as below:

$$0.45(\sigma_{Clean_Hole}) \approx \sigma_{Max_Ballistic_Damage}$$

The absorbed energy appeared to plateau, which indicated that the localized damage reached a saturation point shortly after or at penetration, as shown in Figure 2. Not all of the exit velocities were captured due to impact debris, but enough data points were attained to observe the absorbed energy plateau. NDE testing will be conducted on selected panels to investigate this further, but cross sectional inspection shown below in figure 4 exhibits the radial delamination progression from the impact.

Figure 2: Absorbed Energy as a Function of Impacted Velocity

The samples were inspected post impact for analysis of failure modes. Of the four main energy dissipation modes; there was minimal evidence of shear plugging, and after penetration the fibers in tension were broken. The energy modes of dissipation left included matrix cracking and delamination, which are both matrix dependant. Since the samples were of uniform thickness, the main energy absorption mode was the radial expansion of matrix cracking and delamination. The absorbed energy determined by the change in kinetic energy of the projectile portrayed that the dissipated damage zone energy increased up to penetration, and then appeared to reach saturation. This was most likely due to the thin nature of the panels, as well as the ability for the sample to deform in the gas gun fixture. This could have caused the composite to remain in the lower shear strain thresholds dominated by delamination and secondary fiber deformation. It would appear that to examine failure dominated by shear plugging, the samples would need to be much thicker or more rigidly constrained during impact.

A theoretical model was reported by R. Jones et al., indicating that a critical damage area exists where further damage does not significantly reduce the residual strength [11]. This was later reinforced by Hazell et al., who found that the damage area resulting in thin laminate impacts asymptotes at velocities slightly higher than the ballistic limit. The study went further to show that at extremely high impact velocities (1875 ms⁻¹) the increase in damage area was negligible [5]. As shown below in Figure 3, the cross sectioned impact sites displayed the same approximate delamination zone at velocities greater than the ballistic limit. However, it did appear that more fiber degradation at the impact site occurred at higher velocities. This seemed to have indicated that the area of

impact exhibited a larger strain rate at higher velocities, but the overall delaminated area was rather consistent. It was also observed that the delamination was very small at low velocities and increased to the ballistic limit. Visual inspection of delamination zones was difficult, but the pending C-scan results will be much more conclusive.

Figure 3: *Cross-sectional View of Impact Site at Selected Velocities*

All impacted samples exhibited buckling failure of the impacted primary fibers and (with the exception of very low velocities) partial or complete delamination of the distal tows spanning the exit. This was due to the stitched fabric. While it did allow for compression of straight fibers, potential impact properties that could have been gained from the weave were lost. Comparisons are still valid though due to consistent test panels and the compressive failure mode attained during CAI.

The results for the EG/VE CAI testing are shown below in Figure 4. The ratio of drilled to ballistic strength was 68%. This was higher than that of the CF/VE panels. This may be explained by the additional resin present and that the glass fiber was woven making the structure stiffer.

Figure 4: Ballistic vs Clean-hole Comparison of CAI Strength in EG/VE

CONCLUSIONS

The thin CFRP laminates exhibited a velocity limit after penetration that absorbed constant impact energy, retained a constant residual compressive strength, and appeared to damage a constant area regardless of any appreciable increase in ballistic impact velocity. For the tested laminates, it was found that residual strength associated with the maximum damage was 45% of the clean-hole residual strength. The GF/VE samples displayed a correlation coefficient of 68%. This study showed that determining residual ballistic strength from clean-hole specimens would not be unrealistic. This would eliminate a large need for expensive and imprecise ballistic testing for simple composite geometries.

FUTURE WORK

The influence of thickness, fiber volume fraction, and overlapping damage must still be addressed. Also the effect of fiber matrix interface.

The study will be extended to the impact of pre-stressed composite panels with and without drilled holes.

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